

Demonstration of Intent-Based Networking for End-to-End Packet Optical Cloud-native SDN Orchestration

Ricard Vilalta⁽¹⁾, Daniel Adanza⁽¹⁾, Carlos Manso⁽¹⁾, Pol Alemany⁽¹⁾, Lluís Gifre⁽¹⁾, Ramon Casellas⁽¹⁾, Ricardo Martínez⁽¹⁾, Raul Muñoz⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), ricard.vilalta@cttc.es

Abstract *This demonstration presents a novel Intent Based Networking engine to interact with a Packet Optical SDN controller including Natural Language Processing to translate user commands to control and manage network operations. An interactive User Interface will be demonstrated controlling an emulated Transport SDN network. ©2023 The Author(s)*

Introduction

Intent-based networking (IBN) is a new paradigm for managing packet optical networks. In IBN, network operators define their intent in terms of high-level goals, such as "create a connection between two points", "ensure that all traffic between these two points is protected," or "get all connection that start at the network edge." The IBN system then uses machine learning and other techniques to automatically translate these intents into the specific actions needed to achieve them^[1].

IBN management processes involve intent resolution and intent conflict resolution. Intent resolution involves the use of ML algorithms to analyse user requests and identify appropriate network configurations and actions to meet those needs. The intent common model proposed by TMForum^[2] provides a blueprint for representing business intents as a network-understandable and domain-agnostic entity.

Due to the key role of packet-optical networks to support the high-bandwidth connectivity required by network slicing, the IBN component can be used to optimize backhaul network performance by automatically identifying and prioritizing high-priority traffic and optimizing network resources to meet specific application requirements. This approach can significantly improve the overall network performance and reliability while reducing the complexity and cost of network management and operations.

IBN uses Natural Language Processing (NLP) to extract high-level business intent and translate it into specific network configurations and behaviours^[3]. NLP is a field of computer science that deals with the interaction between computers and human language. NLP techniques can be used to extract information from text, translate languages, and generate natural-sounding text.

NLP is increasingly finding applications in the realm of optical networks, offering numerous benefits. By leveraging NLP techniques, optical network logs can be analyzed effectively to detect potential issues and proactively address them before they escalate. Another valuable application of NLP lies in the translation of network configuration files across different languages, facilitating seamless communication and collaboration between network engineers operating in diverse linguistic environments. Furthermore, NLP can play a vital role in generating network documentation that is both comprehensive and easily comprehensible for humans, enabling efficient knowledge sharing and troubleshooting. Lastly, the integration of NLP in optical networks paves the way for the development of intelligent chatbots capable of answering network-related queries, thus streamlining support processes and enhancing user experience.

Cloud-native SDN (Software-Defined Networking) controllers have revolutionized network management by providing flexibility, scalability, and agility in modern network environments^[4]. To further enhance their capabilities, the introduction of IBN and NLP brings new opportunities for intelligent network orchestration and automation.

This demo presents the integration of a novel NLP component which is able to process both direct audio or text user intents and interact with ETSI TeraFlowSDN controller in order to provide the requested connectivity service intents. In this demo paper we demonstrate in real time and evaluate a complex NLP translation algorithm that is able to provide IBN on top of a packet optical network.

Fig. 1: a) Proposed architecture for Intent-Based Networking for End-to-End Packet Optical Cloud-native SDN Orchestration; and b) Overview of proposed Natural Language Processing solution.

Innovation architecture

Figure 1 (left) shows the envisioned architecture for providing IBN based on NLP on top of a packet optical network using a cloud-native SDN controller. Firstly, we present the Intent NLP component, and secondly, we describe its integration with cloud-native SDN controller.

The main goal of Intent NLP component consists of converting the initial audio or text inputs into a network requests that can be understood by the SDN controller. The generated network requests shall match the requirements enumerated by the user. For this purpose, the Intent NLP component encompasses five sequential steps as shown in Figure 1 (right), consisting of: 1) Voice recognition; 2) Word tokenization; 3) text analysis; 4) providing output and store; and 5) interaction with the ETSI TeraFlowSDN NBI component. We describe them in the following paragraphs.

If necessary, the Intent NLP component includes voice recognition (step 1) to convert the initial audio into machine-readable text that is shown interactively to the user. Then, the solution pre-processes the text and performs word tokenization (step 2) to prepare the data for text analysis. Subsequently, the NLP techniques carry on the task (step 3), performing one-hot encoding to recognize and interpret a wide range of keywords divided into six different categories:

- *operations*: The algorithm distinguishes between three actions: "create", "configure", and "delete" and their respective synonyms.
- *resources*: recognizing the type of resource the user aims to create, such as: "connectivity service", "connection", "link", "nodes", "port" and "bandwidth".

- *locations*: Identifying keywords such as "origin", "destination", "domain" and "port".
- *time*: The solution interprets time restrictions, identifying: dates, hours, minutes, and seconds with different formats and abbreviations.
- *bandwidth restrictions*: The solution recognizes and interprets bandwidth restrictions. For example, for the given input: "medium bandwidth limitation" the system interprets a bandwidth limitation of 20 Gbps., which is the range with a considered intermediate quality.
- *identifiers*: Recognising different numbers working as identifiers. For example, for the text "delete the connection with id 22", the algorithm understands that the user is referring to the connection service identified with the number 22.

Once data has been processed, the input given by the user and its extracted data is stored in the database (step 4). Finally, the solution ensembles the extracted data and parses its information to JSON format, which will be used later to send the required network requests (step 5).

After the user input is translated to network requirements, the Intent NLP component sends a request to create the service identifier to the NBI component in the database by means of the Service component.

After the Intent NLP component receives the service identifier, it requests the NBI the update of the service with the specific endpoints and constraints needed for the connectivity-service.

Then, the Service component initiates the provisioning workflow for a Layer 3 VPN service, which has already been described in^[5], and it finally configures each of the network elements by

Fig. 2: a) GUI of the Intent NLP; b) Histogram of the time spent on the creation of connectivity-services; and c) Wireshark capture of the service provisioning.

the SBI module, using the appropriate driver for each device type. Finally, the database is updated and the answer is returned to the Intent NLP.

Validation and demonstration of the proposed solution

To validate the proposed IBN NLP solution, a basic emulated topology consisting of three access nodes, each of them connected to optical nodes that are in turn connected to a datacenter, has been created. The user can request, using natural language, the creation of a connectivity-service from any of the three access nodes to the datacenter. The user is also able to indicate availability, bandwidth, or duration constraints. To this end, we have extended ETSI TeraFlowSDN^[5] with a new Intent NLP component developed in Python, which uses `speech_recognition` library for audio to text translation, `nltk` for natural language processing and `jinja2`, `json`, and `requests` to interact with ETSI TeraFlowSDN NBI.

Figure 2.a shows the User Interface of the IBN NLP with the text extracted from the audio input and the intent interpretation with its corresponding keywords that will be used to build the requests to the TeraFlowSDN NBI.

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the completed solution, Figure 2.b shows the histogram of the creation of connectivity services from the access nodes to the datacenter using the request created by the user intent. It demonstrates how the services requested from the Intent NLP can be performed between 0.7 and 1.4 seconds, with a mean time around 0.9 seconds. The Intent NLP component introduces around 0.4 seconds of delay to the overall provisioning.

Finally, Figure 2.c shows the Wireshark capture of one of those requested services, showing separately the creation of the connectivity-service in the TeraFlowSDN database in the first two packets (to obtain the service unique identifier), and the update of that service specifying the endpoints and the constraints on the third and fourth packets, finally deploying the service.

The resulting optical connection will be shown in the GUI of CTTC's ONF Transport-API-based Open-Line System (OLS) optical SDN controller.

Conclusions

This paper showcases how an end-to-end multi-layer connectivity-service can be requested by a user, specifying multiple additional constraints using speech recognition and NLP techniques following a IBN approach. This system uses an integrated Intent NLP component into the cloud-native ETSI TeraFlowSDN controller. The demonstration has been done on a multi-layer emulated topology where the user can request connectivity-services between the access nodes and the datacenter using its own voice or written input. The mean time necessary for the provisioning of the end-to-end service is around 0.9 seconds.

Acknowledgements

This work is partially funded by the EC through the Hexa-X-II (101015857) project, the "RE-LAMPAGO grant PID2021-127916OB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF A way of making Europe" and finally, the Spanish UNICO-5G program 6GMICROSDN-NOS (TSI-063000-2021-20) and 6GMICROSDN-CLOUD (TSI-063000-2021-21).

References

- [1] A. Leivadeas and M. Falkner, "A survey on intent based networking", *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 2022.
- [2] T. Forum, "Tr290a intent common model – intent expression v3.1.0", Tech. Rep., 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tmforum.org/resources/technical-report/tr290a-intent-common-model-intent-expression-v3-1-0/>.
- [3] A. S. Jacobs, R. J. Pfitscher, R. H. Ribeiro, *et al.*, "Hey, lumi! using natural language for intent-based network management.", in *USENIX Annual Technical Conference*, 2021, pp. 625–639.
- [4] R. Vilalta, R. Muñoz, R. Casellas, *et al.*, "Teraflow: Secured autonomic traffic management for a tera of sdn flows", in *2021 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 377–382.
- [5] L. Gifre, C. Natalino, S. Gonzalez-Diaz, *et al.*, "Demonstration of zero-touch device and l3-vpn service management using the teraflow cloud-native sdn controller", in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference*, Optica Publishing Group, 2022, M3Z–15.